

Farmer-advisor focus groups for understanding views on novel biodiversity monitoring

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TASK 4.1

Usability assessment of agrobiodiversity data and co-creation of framework for agrobiodiversity-enhancing measures with the rural stakeholders

(M06–M36) Leader: UH; involved: DLG, CUAS, IRWiR PAN, F4S, DLG, FE, BSPB

This task will identify the usefulness and usability of novel agrobiodiversity data and research results collected during the previous WPs from the rural stakeholders' perspective.

These novel agrobiodiversity measures are contrasted with the current agrobiodiversity knowledge (WP1) and utilised stimulus materials in **10 multi-actor focus groups (M06-M18) and co-creation workshops (M24-M36)** with the rural stakeholders in AUT, BGR, FIN, DEU, POL, and PRT (considered in BEL). The proposed dialogue-based method allows spontaneity and interaction between the researchers involved in WPs 2 and 3 and rural stakeholders supporting development of agrobiodiversity measures considering the rural stakeholders' perceptions and expectations.

Thus, the major aims of this task are to create a common understanding of needed agrobiodiversity measures and to engage farmers (supported through WP6) to promote long-term implementation of "new" agrobiodiversity measures in the EU and beyond.

Activities and results of this task will be reported in D4.1 "Rural stakeholder perceptions".

What are focus groups?

- ❖ The focus groups aim to identify and collect versatile perceptions and opinions from grassroots stakeholders about biodiversity and potential adoption of novel biodiversity monitoring technologies.

We also ask about related themes such as view of what constitutes good farming, views on agroforestry, and an ideal future.

- ❖ The focus groups consist of farmers, advisors and the researchers carrying out the research.
- ❖ Focus groups are to be arranged in six BioMonitor4CAP partner countries:
Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Poland and Portugal.

How is focus group data used?

Recommendations used in	Due date
Milestone 11 Advisory booklet on agroforestry implementation	2025.5
D4.1 Report Rural stakeholder perceptions	2025.11
D5.3 Advisory booklet on agri-environmental measures	2026.3
D4.3 .Report Concepts for CAP policy development	2026.11
D4.4 Policy brief	2026.11

Purposive sampling

“Purposive sampling can be used as a way of getting the best information by selecting items or people most likely to have the experience or expertise to provide quality information and valuable insights on the research topic.” (Denscombe 2010)

Participants are chosen based on:

- 1) **Relevance:** to the issue/theory being investigated;
- 2) **Knowledge:** privileged knowledge or experience about the topic.

Participants should:

- ❖ Be knowledgeable about their field of agriculture
- ❖ Have experience with voluntary measures for biodiversity objectives
- ❖ Be ok with speaking in a group (e.g. not too shy, not too dominating of conversation)
- ❖ Groups should include mix of organic and conventional,
- ❖ Aim for gender balance across all 20 participants. Couples can also join.

Process in a nutshell

<p>Focus group: a Semi-structured group interview</p>	<p>5 focus groups, organised by set production sectors</p>	<p>2 farmers and 2 advisors per focus group</p>	<p>1 focus group facilitator. Preferred: Second person to take notes, assist, discuss results afterward</p>
<p>Materials</p>	<p>Protocol: instructions; Information letter; GDPR consent; Background questionnaire</p>	<p>Excel workbook (Contacts & reporting info)</p>	<p>Thematic questions (own page)</p>
<p>Outputs</p>	<p>Excel workbook; Recording of the focus group session</p>	<p>Notes facilitator/researcher(s) (contemporaneous notes and after- discussion)</p>	<p>Summary analysis; Transcription and English translation of transcription</p>

Summary for participants (after analysis- more about this after focus groups are completed)

Five production sectors

- ❖ **PRODUCTION SECTORS** are chosen for their relevance to biodiversity and that the Commission wants agroforestry assessed.
- ❖ Peatland can be skipped if not relevant to your country.
- ❖ If you have another farming system you want to include, such as mixed farming systems, let us know.

Production sectors

Field crops

Dairy

Agro-forestry & Peatland

Garden crops (fruits & veg.)

Grazing (HNV grasslands)

1. Getting started

English language focus group package will be provided (Google Drive WP4).

- Protocol with thematic questions; examples of info letter and written consent; background info needed;
- Excel workbook to manage contacts and provide information on your selection choices;
- Instructions on data storage, transcription and translation (provided later on).

1. Read the protocol and thematic questions. Review the materials in the FocusGroup folder (Google Drive).
Translate the questions (and protocol if necessary). (Machine translation + careful checking against the English version).

2. Create a suitable information letter for potential participants.

3. Create a list of potential participants. If challenging, first *create a list of sources of potential participants*.

4. Create a written consent form and decide on format (email, in-person, online survey, etc).

5. Translate the short background information form and decide how you are going to collect the background information (email, in-person, online survey, etc).

2. Reaching out to stakeholders

Identify your stakeholder groups and your strategy: own contacts, reaching out to professional organisations/networks, registry of agricultural advisors, snowball incl. recommendations from advisors.

Diversity & dynamics: Do you have sufficient diversity (e.g. regional, farm structure, farming approach, age, gender) and people with good group discussion skills (not too quiet, not too domineering)?

Selection: Do you have a clear reason why someone is included? We will ask for this!

Reaching out: Are you contacting multiple people at once (e.g. your first choices) or one at a time?

Contact method: How are you contacting farmers and advisors: E-mail, telephone, sms, other?

Set a meeting: in person or online? Flexible or fixed dates? Do the stakeholders have necessary equipment, skills, infrastructure for online meetings or ability to meet in person?

Send calendar invitation and link. If necessary, confirm receipt of invitation & participation.

2. Data management

- Excel workbook with examples: Download it and use it for data management.
- You can add columns as necessary and change the red titles to your own country's information.
- We will request the Excel with other materials later on.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Country	Contact	Focus group	Advisor? (Y/N)	ADVISORY REGISTRY(Y/N)	Farmer? (Y/N)	Organic (Y/N)	Participation	Organisation	Production specialisations (FINNISH FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY)	Title (e.g. ProAgria)	Advisory sections (FINNISH FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY)	Justification/expe rtise	Tel.	e-mail	web
FINLAND	ADVISOR 1	Grazing	Y	Y	-		Yes. Thurs. 12/14/2023 @ 14:00 16:00	ProAgria	DAIRY PRODUCTION, BEEF PRODUCTION, SHEEP AND GOAT PRODUCTION, CROP PRODUCTION, HORSES.	LANDSCAPE AND NATURE MANAGEMENT SPECIALIST; NEUVO ENVIRONMENT SPECIALIST	ENVIRONMENT	EXPERT IN SEMI- NATURAL GRASSLAND NAAGEMENT AND OTHER FARMLAND BIODIVERSITY MANAGEMENT PLANNING			

- Save your recordings! Teams automatically saves the recording, but it may set a very short expiration date. You can change the expiration date manually to never expire.
- We'll cover transcriptions and translations in another training.

3. Focus group schedule

Time per theme may vary, but pay attention and keep to the 50 min and 1:30 marks so there is sufficient time to discuss monitoring (40 min), final topics (30 min) and close the session.

28.01.24

Approach is conversational, relaxed, but structured by the themes and 2h time limit

1. Welcome, recording → 2 min
2. Introduction round → 3 min
3. Good farming → 10 min
4. Biodiversity understanding and attitudes → 15 min
5. Key biodiversity challenges → 15 min

-----**45 to 50 minute mark**-----

6. Biodiversity monitoring → 30 min
7. Monitoring time and resources → 10 min

-----**1:30h mark**-----

30 minutes for the following topics

8. Agroforestry
9. Future
10. Advice from farmers to farm advisors, advisors' advice to farmers
11. Final comments from participants.

-----**2:00h mark**-----

4. Themes, questions and prompts

THEME is the subject of discussion and your reference for keeping track of time.

QUESTIONS need to be answered. Good to ask them directly.

PROMPTS are questions we wanted to include, but we have a time limit. Use as needed to facilitate conversation. Keep an eye on them and see if they get answered and if you have time to ask them.

Theme **5. Key biodiversity challenges in your agricultural sector (15 min.)**

Questions *What are the main challenges facing your agricultural sector/production, both in general and in terms of biodiversity?*

- In what ways do biodiversity challenges become visible and impact your activities?

Prompts **CHALLENGES PROMPTS**

- Who are the key actors that improve or hinder actions for biodiversity?

- How do these challenges affect your ability or potential to take biodiversity into account in agriculture?

- What is the sector doing for biodiversity and who (organisations or mechanisms) are promoting or slowing down biodiversity improvement?

- What factors facilitate or challenge the implementation of biodiversity measures on farms? (if already answered in the previous questions, use the question to draw the theme together).

- What are the main sources of information on agri-environmental biodiversity in your production sector? Who (which organisations) do you rely on to provide this information?

On-Farm Biodiversity Monitoring

Slide on screen for the duration of the focus group session

Soil sampling package

eDNA barcoding

- For soil sampling at pre-defined spots on the farm
- Pre-paid return envelope

Optical: Camera

- Collect memory cards
- Upload videos to server
- Charge batteries

Traditional methods

- Bird counts
- Transect walks
- Traps

Remote sensing

Periodic sensing with optical, radar and quadcopter-based tools

- Wireless internet connection
- Technical know-how/service
- Battery charging

Acoustic: Audiomoth

- Collect memory cards
- Upload videos to server
- Charge batteries

Other methods, ideas?

- Innovative biodiversity monitoring methods

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Summary

Establish focus groups	2 farmers and 2 advisors per focus group + facilitator & assistant	Information letter, GDPR permission, Contact Excel, Background questionnaire	Prepare your materials, set a time, test your technology
Carry out the focus group	FOLLOW THE PROTOCOL- stay on script and pay attention to time	Introduction, permission to record, TURN RECORDING ON	SAVE THE RECORDING, have after-discussion & summarize the main points and observations
After the focus group	CHECK YOUR RECORDING WON'T EXPIRE	Generate an mp3 audio file for transcription.	Carry out the transcription and English translation of transcription
Data management	Make sure you have GDPR consent and background info from participants	SECURE SAVE: Recording, transcripts, original & English translation of transcript, your notes and an English summary, contact Excel, GDPR & background info	Send requested materials to Traci & Toni or upload to secure data repository as instructed

